

Workshop Data Stewards Job Profiles

4 April 2023

Holland Heart House, Utrecht

Programme

13.00 - 13.20 *Welcome and opening* by Hans de Jonge, Quartermaster-Director Regieorgaan Open Science & Sarah Coombs, Open Science advisor for the Universities of Applied Sciences.

13.20 - 13.30 *Introduction to the 2021 “Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands” report, its recommendations, and the Data stewards job profile*; Mijke Jetten, Community Manager Data Stewardship (DTL) & Program Manager FAIR Data Health-RI

13.30 - 14.15 *Use cases on data stewards job profile implementation*

- Radboudumc, Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Professor Bioinformatics
- Saxion UoAS, Renate Mattizsik, Research Data Management Advisor
- TU Delft, Yan Wang, Data Stewardship Coordinator

14.15 - 14.30 *Introduction to the international landscape*

- EOSC Task Force on Data Stewardship; Celia van Gelder, Network manager TDCC LSH / Training Programme Manager Health-RI
- RDA Professionalising Data Stewards Interest Group; Yan Wang, TU Delft

14.30 - 14.50 Coffee / tea break

14.50- 15.40 *Break out discussions*

15.40 - 16.00 *Central wrap-up and future actions*

13.00 - 13.20 Welcome and opening

Hans de Jonge, Director Open Science NL

Sarah Coombs, Open Science advisor Universities of Applied Sciences

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Workshop Data Stewards Job Profiles: Build and Sustain Capacity for FAIR Implementation

Hans de Jonge | April 4 2023 | Holland Heart House

Overview

- From NPOS to (“regieorgaan”) Open Science NL
 - Where we come from
 - Future plans
- Some reflections on data stewardship in the NLs

Launch of Open Science NL

Actueel › Nieuws › Regieorgaan Open Science officieel van start onder de naam Open Science NL

Regieorgaan Open Science officieel van start onder de naam Open Science NL

23 maart 2023

Vertegenwoordigers van vijftien kennisinstellingen en het ministerie van OCW hebben het convenant voor Open Science NL ondertekend. Hierin staan nadere afspraken over het nieuw op te zetten regieorgaan Open Science bij NWO, dat Open Science NL heet. De feestelijke ondertekening vond plaats tijdens een bijeenkomst aan de TU in Delft, dat geheel in het teken stond van open science.

Met de ondertekening van het convenant is het nieuw op te richten regieorgaan een feit. Het doel van

Towards a “regieorgaan” Open Science at NWO

3.3 Kennis delen en benutten

3.3.1 Open science en open education

Open science en open education moeten de norm worden in hoger onderwijs en onderzoek, zoals het Coalitieakkoord stelt. Academisch werk moet vrij toegankelijk en gemakkelijk benaderbaar zijn en de dialoog tussen onderzoekers, docenten en burgers moet worden gestimuleerd. Vrije en veilige uitwisseling van ideeën tussen onderzoekers en maatschappelijke partijen is namelijk essentieel voor excellente wetenschapsbeoefening en draagt bij aan betere kwaliteit van wetenschappelijke kennis. Deze doelstellingen komen samen in de transities naar open science en open education, die zich momenteel nog in verschillende stadia bevinden. Om de transitie naar open science, die in het afgelopen decennium al is ingezet, extra kracht bij te zetten, verken ik met NWO de oprichting van een ‘Regieorgaan Open Science’, waarbij ik uiteraard ook in gesprek ga met het veld. Met dit orgaan kunnen inspanningen op nationaal niveau beter afgestemd, gebundeld en gecoördineerd worden. Het orgaan krijgt het beheer over € 20 miljoen per jaar om een impuls te geven aan de transitie, voor de looptijd van het Fonds voor Onderzoek en Wetenschap. Daarna moet open science de norm zijn en moet het volledig zijn opgenomen in de werkwijze van universiteiten en andere kennisinstellingen.

What is a “regieorgaan” in the NWO context?

- Construction / instrument to provide temporary but long-time (i.e. at least 10 years) support to a subject, field or discipline.
- Other examples: SIA, NRO and earlier ICT, Brain & Cognition, Genomics.
- In close collaboration with “the field”.
- Embedded within the NWO organization but with a large degree of autonomy. Meaning: its own governance, office, strategy and funding instruments.
- Main task: funding, but also additional coordinating activities.

Mission of Open Science NL:

“ To advance and accelerate Open Science in the Netherlands with the goal of making Open Science the norm. ”

Mission of Open Science NL:

“ To advance and accelerate Open Science in the Netherlands with the goal of making Open Science the norm. ”

- By providing (temporary) **funding** for projects, initiatives and infrastructures
- By **monitoring** and evaluating progress
- By providing a forum for **exchange** of best practice
- By organising and facilitating **coordination** on national level

Team

Jeroen Sondervan | Open
Scholarly Communication

Marta Teperek | FAIR data

Maria Cruz | Open Research
Software

Frederike Schmitz | Citizen
Science & public engagement

Mark van Assem | Program
officer

Jeroen Scharroo |
Communications

Merie Pelsser | Secretary

How we will work

NPOS agenda provides overall framework

Work programme
2023-2024

To be approved by Steering board, based on consultation with the community on various levels

Funding
instrument
s

A diverse array of instruments, tailored to the needs of the topic and community

What Open Science NL will do on Data Stewardship?

Some reflections on current state of DS in the NLs

- Capacity seems to be growing but a lot of DS still seem to do the job without having the role / job profile?
- High turnover of staff. Difficulties in retaining DS?
- Reluctance / difficulty to provide permanent contracts?
- Need for a dedicated recognition & rewards program(line) for support staff.
- So, should there be a professional association for DS in NL. See Society for Research Software Engineering in the UK.

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Questions?

Professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands: competences, training and education

Dutch roadmap towards national implementation of FAIR data stewardship
Mijke Jetten, mijke.jetten@health-ri.nl

Dutch roadmap towards professionalising data stewardship

“Invest 5% of research funds in ensuring data are reusable. It is irresponsible to support research but not data stewardship. (...) Many top universities are starting to see that the costs of not sharing data are significant and greater than the associated risks. Data stewardship offers excellent returns on investment.” ([Barend Mons](#), GO FAIR/CODATA)

Data stewardship and data management skills are essential in research. **Challenges:**

- There is no consensus on the responsibilities and tasks of data stewards, and formal profiles (including knowledge, skills and abilities (KSAs)) are lacking
- No/too little and/or not findable tailored education & training
- This hampers the adequate capacity building and complicates efficient data management which are necessary for open science implementation
- (Inter)national alignment and coordination are needed to achieve coherent training and education, accompanied with a consistent human resource (HR) policy

The NPOS F [data stewardship report](#) was written by over 30 representatives of universities, university medical centres (UMCs), universities of applied sciences (UASs), service providers and representatives of Dutch umbrella organisations.

How much capacity is needed? Still a very long way to go!

Role	Task	FTEs needed per 1000 researchers
Data Steward	Assisting researchers with effective management of research data	26
Trainer on data stewardship	Training researchers on data management skills	4

That is 3 FTE per 100 researchers!

Number adapted from [OECD](#) (2020), "Building digital workforce capacity and skills for data-intensive science"

The [EC High Level Expert Group EOSC](#) estimated 5 FTE per 100 researchers

12. How many DataStewards/Managers/Research Supporters (strategic, generic, embedded, centrally)(but not RSE or data scientist)does your organization have in relation to scientific staff ?

19 antwoorden

- 1 fte in relation to 500 scientific staff, including PhD (or even less).
- 1 fte in relation to 100-500 fte scientific staff (including PhD).
- 1 fte or more in relation to scientific 100 fte scientific staff (including PhD).

Landelijk Coördinatiepunt
Research Data Management

Results of LCRDM "[Do I PASS for FAIR](#)" 2020 survey

Previous reports

The NPOS report builds upon the widely supported outcomes and recommendations of two previous projects (2019), i.e. the ZonMw data stewardship project and the LCRDM data stewardship project

LCRDM data stewardship task areas

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2669150>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3066366>

NPOS/ELIXIR data stewardship roles in the data stewardship landscape

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3474789>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3243909>

Landscape analysis on training and education

8 case studies (universities, UASs & UMCs) as a first fact check on data stewardship training and education in the Netherlands

Recommendations

1. Care for your data steward
2. Community, networking and proximity to peers
3. Coordinated approach
4. Flexibility in the job

Basic data steward job profile components

Annexes

- Areas, responsibilities, tasks & competences
- Basic components UFO (universities)
- Three local profiles for FUWAVAZ (UMCs)
- Proposal UASs DS job profile
- Basic components RSE job profile (cf. DCCs)

Recommendations

1. Formalise profiles
2. Adopt profiles
3. Create career perspectives
4. Allow diversity of roles and types
5. Adopt good practices
6. Secure positions

Training, education & certification / data steward skills tool

- Inventory of training resources & pilot annotation of courses based on competences
- Inventory of certification mechanisms (courses, trainees, trainers & organisations)
→ in early days & to be done in global alignment
- Sketch for a data steward skills tool as a single point of reference for data steward competences, training and education (with 5 DS personas)
- In collaboration with ELIXIR, DS competences added to the EBI [Competency Hub](#) tool (expertise areas, responsibilities, tasks, KSAs, and learning objectives)
→ expand to learning paths connected to courses

Recommendations

1. Standardise metadata for training
2. Align with (inter)national certification initiatives & providers

National level

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		For universities but not yet formalised for UMC and UAS	Dependency on formal job classification systems
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		Local and national communities (TDCC + Data Stewards Interest Group)	Strengthen collaboration and peer-to-peer learning
3.	Build data steward capacity		Disbalance: necessary and current FTE	Harmonise efforts + convincing stories
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		No certification + strengthen collaboration on a national level	Potential for initiatives such as RDNL, TDCCs and Open Science NL
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		Hiring and keeping DS is challenging	Support vs science embedment discussion

Data stewardship profile implementation in Radboudumc

Peter-Bram 't Hoen

Professor of Bioinformatics (and FAIR data infrastructure)

Medical BioSciences

Radboudumc

A short history

- This started some 7-8 years when at LUMC. We hired the first data stewards but did not have an appropriate job description.
- Discussions with HR on definition of data steward, research software engineer, data scientist and data analyst profiles
- Continued at Radboudumc with Romy Geldof and Aloys Klein Gunnewiek

Timeline

- 2019: Approached HR with function descriptions; initial discussions; need for different levels
- 2020: Drafting and revision of profiles with HR and Leeuwendaal
- 2021: Internal review by different departments; official grading by Leeuwendaal
- Approval by director HR
 - Internal communication with HR advisors
- 2022: First employees appointed as data steward

In parallel: discussion in NFU – FUWAVAZ coordination team and NPOS Data Steward task group

Different Job profiles

a: (scale 9) Hands-on supporting research projects

b: (scale 10) Additional responsibilities for implementation of data stewardship policies in research programs

c: (scale 11) Additional responsibilities for defining data stewardship policies in a research institute

Numbers of employees appointed

- As data steward: 7 (in a and b)
- As data analyst: 5 (in a and b)

Current status

- 7 employees appointed as data steward
- Many more data stewards working at Radboudumc (although some more in a role than in a function)
- Data steward network functions well, coordinated by RTC Data Stewardship (Mirjam Brullemans)
- Links to data stewards at Radboud University established (RDM)
- Training of data stewards mostly informal ('on the job'); focus on creating awareness and training of researchers
- In my group: "Friday data steward day"

Successes

- The first UMC with full implementation of data steward job profiles

Challenges

- **Lack of awareness** of the data steward profiles in certain departments and with some HR advisors
- **Difference with data manager** function profiles is often unclear
- **The career path a, b, c does not fit every data steward**: it is assuming that data stewards would like to gradually move from more hands-on project-related data stewardship to more policy-related activities.
- Data steward is **not recognised as a research function**. This means that we can only appoint data stewards for three years on a temporary contract instead of four and is a reason for using alternative profiles
- Data stewards **do not have a knowledge worker status**. This makes it difficult to recruit data stewards from outside EU when they are >30

Use case: Radboudumc

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		Implemented in local FUWAVAZ	Implemented in national FUWAVAZ
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		Local Data Steward Network and national Data Steward Interest group function well	In addition to internal network, create a face to the outside world (Professional society of data stewards)
3.	Build data steward capacity		Training from peer-peer; too little advanced courses available	Involved in development of expert trainings
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		Training mostly on-the-job	Organise advanced-level trainings and accreditation system
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		Not sure whether the career path a, b, c profiles fit every data steward	No concrete actions at the moment

A photograph of a hospital hallway. In the foreground, a metal gurney is partially visible, covered with a clear plastic sheet. A white label with the text "Radboudumc" is attached to the gurney. In the background, a nurse in white scrubs is walking away from the camera. The hallway has large windows and yellow pillars.

Radboudumc

Radboudumc

Data Stewardship at Saxion

University of Applied Sciences

Renate Mattszik (r.mattszik@saxion.nl)

- Data Librarian/Data Steward since 2018
- Saxion Research Services
- DCC-PO working groep member for Data Stewardship and training

December 1, 2021 – November 30, 2022 + 1 year extension

Started with 6 working groups:

- Organization data stewardship
- FAIR DATA
- From a DCC to a future HUB
- Set up of Data Science Care Team
- ICT
- Communication

Objectives:

- Coordinating and professionalizing data stewardship for Universities of Applied Sciences at a national level.
- Promoting and facilitating data-intensive research in higher professional education (such as big data/IoT/machine learning/high performance computer etc).
- Taking a first step towards a sustainable national knowledge and advice hub by joining forces around RDM, research software and infrastructure.

Job Profile Data Steward at UoAS:

History:

2020-2021: NPOS F

feb 2021-nov. 2022: DCC-PO: 13 UoAS from working group Organization Data Stewardship worked on [Handreiking voor de Organisatie van Datastewardship voor praktijkgericht onderzoek van hogescholen](#)

The report was presented to the Advies College Open Science of the VH.

UAS Job Profile: 8 expertise areas and 3 levels: junior/executive tasks, coordinating tasks and policy tasks

Policy & Strategy	Compliance	Facilitating Good RDM Practices	RDM Service Management
RDM Infrastructure	Knowledge Management	Network and Communication	Data Sharing and Publishing

Use case: Saxion

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No official formalization • HR approved of profile for job offer 	HR is looking into revising all job profiles concerning research
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SRS website and back office • RDM policy • no other tasks 	
3.	Build data steward capacity		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of sufficient funding • Discussion with management about higher job profiling 	Positioning library
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDNL • Training DCC-PO • DCC Spring Training days • Plenty on the job training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving training myself • DCC-PO Edubadges
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I am the only one right now • I am already at the highest level 	Is playing a role as soon as other DSs are employed.

Challenges

- Every UoAS has its own job profile system
- Uniformity
- Funding
- Positioning within the organization
- Capacity building
- Necessity!

Implementing UFO Data Steward profile at TU Delft

Yan Wang, Data Stewardship Coordinator, TU Delft Library

y.wang-16@tudelft.nl

Outline

- Implementation approach
- Current status of the profile implementation
- Data Steward recruitment and onboarding
- Challenges
- Reflection on the NPOS recommendations

TU Delft Data Stewardship model

Objectives

- Cultural change
- Disciplinary needs in RDM

Pilot 2017 – 2020

Standard service since 2020

Team composition & profile

- 11 + 1 Data Stewards
- 1 Coordinator

Implementation approach at TU Delft

UFO profile adoption

- 7-8 out of 12 Data Stewards have adopted the UFO profile
- UFO project has been used in recruitment since 2022
- To Do
 - Update all Data Stewards' profile
 - Assess and update Data Stewardship coordinator's profile

Recruitment and on-boarding

		2017/18	2020 - now
Recruitment	Job description	Main tasks remain the same in job description	
			More details / faculty-specific focuses
	Candidates	Research background, current PhD / postdoc	
		1 with RDM support experience	2 with RDM support experience
On-boarding	Training	Many joined the Essentials 4 Data Support Training from library colleagues	Follow online training materials
	On job education	Team discussion & Peer-support	

Challenges in relation to profile adoption

- Difference between profile and position
- Data Stewards' tasks vary across faculties in daily practices, library HR recommendation can only be generic on the 'common tasks' (baseline).
- Divide between academic and support roles in UFO system

Reflection on NPOS recommendations

nr	Recommendation	Current state (only symbol)	Explanation current state	(Near) Future state Steps to go
1.	Formalization of job profile data steward		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UFO profile is used in new recruitment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complete the profile update for existing DS
2.	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well established DS team - Good visibility to researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve communication channels and internal management
3.	Build data steward capacity		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Central and faculty level capacity in place (generic) - Lack of capacity on innovation - Lack of capacity at departmental / project level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and establish faculty level Data Stewardship
4.	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A lot of materials and on job learning available. - But no certified formal education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish formal on-boarding for DS
5.	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Salary scale up from UFO profile adoption - No clear career path for DS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow EOSC and RDA work on DS career path

EOOSC & Data Stewardship

04 | 04 | 2023 Data Stewardship Profiles workshop Utrecht, NL

Celia van Gelder (Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences, Co-chair EOOSC Task Force Data Stewardship Curricula and Career Paths)

European Open Science Cloud - EOSC

- The ambition of the European Open Science Cloud, known as EOSC, is to develop a 'Web of FAIR Data and Services' for science in Europe.
- EOSC will be a multi-disciplinary environment where researchers can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services, enabling them to better conduct their work.
- EOSC builds on existing infrastructure and services supported by the European Commission, Member States and research communities. It brings these together in a federated 'system of systems' approach, adding value by aggregating content and enabling services to be used together.
- <https://eosc.eu/>

[Report](#) (February 2021)

Main recommendations of the EOSC

Training & Skills Working Group:

- Utilise the **Framework of Actors** in the EOSC Ecosystem in the development and mainstreaming of FAIR and open science skills and training
 - **Coordinate and align relevant skills curricula and training frameworks**
 - Encourage and support the **competence centres approach** for FAIR and open science training
 - Facilitate **increased integration of FAIR and open science courses with university qualifications**
 - Build a **learning and training catalogue** to maximise interoperability.
 - Include learning and training resources in the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EIF)
 - Develop an EOSC Skills and Training Leadership Programme
-
- In addition the report gives specific recommendations for the different stakeholders
 - Policy makers & funders, Universities & research organisations, Competence centres , EOSC Association, EOSC projects

Data Stewardship Roles

Description of 10 roles within the EOSC ecosystem, one situational example for each role and a list of required skills

Use Case: Emerging approaches towards implementing FAIR data stewardship in Europe

In the past years, it has become clear that there is a large need for, and shortage of, individuals with Open Science and data stewardship expertise within research organisations. This is evident in all research domains and also transcends the institutional and even the national level. For this reason, a lot of effort has recently been put into professionalising data stewardship, bringing together national and global approaches, and both discipline-specific and discipline-agnostic efforts. However, the implementation of these data stewardship competences, education and certification in higher education institutions (HEIs) and research-performing organisations (RPOs) is still in an early stage.

Substantial work related to data stewardship competences, training and education has already been done in two European countries, which may serve as the basis for the EOSC Skills agenda for data stewardship. In Denmark, national recommendations have been provided to gather evidence for supporting pre-qualifications for data steward education at universities [Wildgaard 2020] and the first Master in Data Stewardship is expected to start in September 2021. In the Netherlands, a community-endorsed data stewardship competency framework was developed and recommendations for national implementation of a national FAIR Data Stewardship Roadmap have been formulated, which can now be taken further by the national stakeholders [Scholtens 2019; Jetten 2021].

The roles and stakeholders in the data stewardship landscape that emerged from both efforts align very well and are shown in Figure 6.2 below.

Figure 6.2: Roles of data stewards in the data stewardship landscape in Denmark and the Netherlands [DS_Roles]

EOSC is in an excellent position to coordinate and to support Member States in building the data stewardship capacity that is needed. Two major complementary actions are required to close the skills gap with respect to data stewardship, and EOSC can play a crucial role in both. First, it is essential to train future data stewards based on an accredited curriculum in Europe's universities. Second, current professionals in the field need to be (up-)skilled and proper career paths for data stewardship need to be defined and acknowledged. By ensuring research groups access the help of data stewards, research outputs will be more effectively managed and shared, ensuring higher quality, reproducibility and more consistent long-term sharing and reuse.

Use case in Skills Chapter of the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA, 2021, chapter 6.4) of the EOSC: "Emerging approaches towards implementing FAIR data stewardship in Europe"

EOSC Association – 2022 Advisory Groups & Task Forces

- Implementation of EOSC
 - Rules of Participation compliance monitoring
 - PID policy and implementation
 - Researcher engagement and adoption
- Technical challenges on EOSC
 - Technical interoperability of data and services
 - Infrastructure for quality research software
 - AAI Architecture
- Metadata and data quality
 - Semantic interoperability
 - FAIR metrics and data quality
- **Research careers and curricula**
 - **Data stewardship curricula and career paths**
 - **Research careers, recognition and credit**
 - **Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC**
- Sustaining EOSC
 - Defining funding models for EOSC
 - Long-term data preservation

<https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups>

Chairs

Celia van Gelder
DTL

Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi
TU Graz

Board Liaison

Wilhelm Widmark
Stockholm University

- 25 members (+ 5 new members in 2022)
 - experts from 18 European countries and main stakeholder groups: universities, national organisations/initiatives/infrastructures, EOSC related projects, research infrastructures
- Co-chairs: Ilire Hasani-Mavriqi, Vera Matser (until April 2022), Celia van Gelder (from April 2022)

The Data stewardship, curricula and career paths Task Force focuses on the role of data stewards, their core activities, and curricula to ensure that they are internationally recognized and aligned

Members

Basaltì, Chiara UNIBO	Bianchini, Federico University of Oslo	Blümel, Ina TIB	Blumer, Eliane EPFL
Bracco, Laetitia University of Lorraine	Claes, Nathalie KU Leuven	Cournede, Constance Université de Nantes	Fazekas-Paragh, Judit University of Debrecen
Forni, Monica University of Bologna	Frontini, Francesca CLARIN ERIC	Galik, Malgorzata Jagiellonian University	Gurwitz, Kim EMBL-EBI
Janik, Joanna CRNS	Kalová, Tereza University of Vienna	Kuchma, Iryna OpenAIRE	Legat, Dunja University of Maribor
Lindroos, Hanna Swedish University of Agricultural sciences	Luetcke, Henry ETH Zürich	Meeus, Joke FWO	Pinnick, Jaana NGCD
Szuffita-Żurawska, Magdalena Gdańsk University of Technology	Thorpe, Deborah University College Cork	Ward, Robyn University of Nottingham	Walek, Anna Gdańsk University of Technology
Wildgaard, Lorna Copenhagen University Library			

TF focus and approach

- The TF has two main work streams:
 - minimal curriculum for data stewards
 - career paths for data stewards
- In addition, the TF advises the EOSC-A Board about a.o. the MAR and SRIA

Our approach

- Actively engage with stakeholders and build on previous work: build, connect & consolidate
 - Examples: the RDA Group on Professionalizing Data Stewardship, EUA, other EOSC-A Task forces, and relevant projects (Skills4EOSC, EOSC-Future, etc)
- Identify (existing and new) use cases implementing data stewardship curricula and career paths
- Ensure a co-creation process between theoretical development and implementation examples
- Make current insights, experiences, implementation examples available (in a usable form) for all stakeholders

SRIA & MAR

The overall purpose of the EOSC **Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)** is to define the general framework for future research, development and innovation activities in relation to the European Open Science Cloud. This framework will be further developed in the context of the EOSC Partnership, drawing on inputs from EOSC Association member organisations and Task Forces.

The SRIA is of interest to all the individuals and organisations interested in or impacted by EOSC, both now and within the timeframe of Horizon Europe. This includes research-performing organisations, research funders, service providers, governmental organisations, companies/businesses and citizens. Naturally the European Commission is also a key stakeholder for the SRIA as it is used to inform the work programmes via the **Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR)**, which forms Section 8 of the SRIA.

The current version of the SRIA (1.1) was finalised in November 2022.

Recommendations for Data Stewardship Skills, Training and Curricula

Milestone report from curriculum workstream - expected April 2023

- Led by: Iryna Kuchma
- Applying the following lenses: national case studies & institutional case studies (RPOs)
- For each case study/stakeholder/lens:
 - a consolidation of relevant reports
 - current implementation status
 - recommendations/challenges/best practices
- National/institutional use cases/case studies so far: Austria, Denmark, France, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, **the Netherlands**, Switzerland and the UK
 - *Netherlands- still needs to be written!*

Career Paths Workstream

- Led by Tereza Kalova and Franscesca Frontini
- Two activities
 - Analysis of data stewardship career paths
 - *intermediate report*
 - Workshop together with RDA IG Professionalizing Data Stewardship
 - *preparatory meeting (online) - September 2023*
 - *intention: workshop at RDA Plenary Salzburg, October 2023*

Contact

- EOSC TF Data Stewardship Curricula and Career Paths:
stewardship-tf@eosc.eu
- <https://www.eosc.eu/advisory-groups/data-stewardship-curricula-and-career-paths>

Professionalising Data Stewardship Interests Group

IG co-chairs (presenter Yan Wang, TU Delft)

Slides source: RDA PDS IG

Professionalising Data Stewardship IG

Motivation

- Lack of consensus on DS's responsibility, value, required knowledge and skills
- No clear approach on building and keeping the DS capacity

PDS IG Co-Chairs

[Graham Parton](#), Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA), Senior Environmental Data Scientist, graham.parton@stfc.ac.uk

[Romain David](#), European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents, Research fellow, data manager, romain.david@erinha.eu

[Yan Wang](#), Delft University of Technology, Data Stewardship Coordinator, y.wang-16@tudelft.nl

RDA PDS IG History

P14 & VP15

BoF sessions, initial challenges identified, PDS IG [charter](#) written, task groups formed

VP16

map interdependencies, prioritize

VP17

working sessions to advance tasks #1-#3

VP18 - Update and Roadmap

VP19 - Roundup and Next Phase discussions

Data Stewardship as a Profession

TG5
Research Landscape of DS Training

TG6
Data Steward Career Tracks

Data Stewardship as a Service

TG1
Business Case

TG3
Data Stewardship Models

RDA IG PDS outputs

- TG3 Data Stewardship Models
 - Report: [Current Models of Data Stewardship Survey Report](#) (2022)
 - Dataset: [Models of Data Stewardship Survey Output Data](#) (2022)
- TG5 Research Landscape of Data Stewardship training
 - Report: [Data Stewardship Landscape report](#) (2022)
 - Dataset: Landscape report [resource matrix](#) (2022)

RDA IG PDS Work in Progress

- TG6 Data Steward Career Tracks
 - Survey on Data Steward Career Tracks (June 2022 – now)

For people who currently work on data steward-related activities:

*205 respondents (~74%) do not have the job title 'data steward' **

* this is a very preliminary result which may not be accurate. .

Break

14.50- 15.40 Break out discussions

1. How to successfully implement the data stewards job profile and recruit data stewards?
1. How to organise national training and collaborate to increase capacity?

Report back on actionable step(s)

> sticky notes or slides (shorturl.at/egisx)

Breakout group 1

Actions to take - related to job profile

- Clarity about the role

Actions to take - related to training and capacity

- Have acknowledged certification for the data stewards (example privacy officers)
- Professional training
- Data engineers education

Certification can be complex notion; domain should be taken into account

Breakout group 2

Actions to take - related to job profile

- Maybe too much attention to the job title instead of tasks list; research is evolving and new tasks arise, senior management not always aware. How to convince them; difference between faculties. What is mechanism to convince boards?
- Find ambassadors / e.g. deans
- Competition can help: show open data sets; software etc. (open science achievements)
- Compliance vs FAIR data
 - move from compliance to societal responsibility?

Actions to take - related to training and capacity

- National training

Breakout group 3

Actions to take - related to job profile

- meaningful: create stories while collaborating (hanging out) with the communities
- awareness: team up with HR people for instance (by coordinators / research support head)
- sustainability: it should be mandatory to use 'overhead' (15%) from research project funding for structural data stewardship support! Requires system change

Actions to take - related to training and capacity

Wrap-up and future actions

nr	Recommendation	Status	Next steps
1	Formalization of job profile data steward		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create clarity on the data stewardship tasks • Make open science achievements such as open data or software competitive to make the case for investing in data stewardship for (faculty) boards
2	Data stewards are well organized and easy to find		
3	Build data steward capacity		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Team up with all stakeholders in your organization, including HR staff and senior researchers or deans who can act as ambassadors for data stewardship • Find funds for structural and sustainable data stewardship support
4	Ensure the availability of (certified) education and training of data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up acknowledged professional training for data stewards and explore if a professional association is desirable (cf. software engineering societies or privacy officers associations)
5	Use job profiles for career perspective data stewards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make FAIR and data stewardship meaningful by focusing less on compliance and more on societal responsibility • Allow data stewards time to be part of the research team and recognize their efforts as part of the team's work